

A SURVEY ON PREVALENT CONFLICT MANAGEMENT STYLES AND DOMINANT SCHOOL CLIMATE OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract: This study aimed to find out the Prevalent Conflict Management Styles and the Dominant School Climate of Public Elementary School. The study used a descriptive survey method research design. A survey questionnaire was used to gather the data desired. Frequency count, percentage and weighted mean were the statistical tools used. Based on the analysis of the gathered data, the Prevalent Conflict Management Style of Public Elementary School is collaborating. The dominant school climate of public elementary school is autonomous. The result further reveals that public elementary schools exhibit distinct conflict management styles and school climate. It further bared that educational background and the number of years in service of administrator also plays significantly to its conflict management styles and school climate. The prevalent conflict management style of public elementary school is collaborating which exemplifies that the administrator can work jointly with others especially in an intellectual endeavor. Meanwhile the dominant school climate is autonomous which illustrates that the administrators provide freedom in decision-making, within a pre-agreed management framework.

Keywords: Prevalent conflict management style and the dominant school climate of public elementary school, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conflict is integral to human relationships. Every member of every organization has different roles to perform that involve different conflict styles. Job guidance, compensation, monitoring, discipline, and performance assessment often include the use of conflict management forms. Most people believe organizational change and control will cause tension. As a causal factor, they introduce a battle to clarify the dynamics of an organization phenomenon. Conflict variations in interpretation yield implication on their own. A superior can use different conflict styles depending on subordinates' responses or reaction to these styles.

As a superior, he/she must be conscious of the presence of multiple sources of conflict in work situations and how he/she maintains the job satisfaction of subordinates because discontent could lead to many organizational dysfunctions, such as decreased work efficiency, dissatisfaction, absenteeism, high turnover and job stress (Lee, 2010).

Workplace conflict for workers arising from differences in personalities and beliefs of employees is a normal occurrence. Promptness in coping with employee conflict is important to a healthy work climate. Believing that dispute would vanish is a false belief on the part of the workers because if not treated properly, it may develop into major problems. Managers should consider the common causes of employee conflict before conflicts become unmanageable (Johnson, 2009).

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As every other organization, schools are also vulnerable to conflict, which can affect their environment. School climate varies widely. While some schools feel welcoming, supportive, and friendly, others feel unwanted, excluded, and even dangerous. School climate issues outlooks and orientation drawn on the atmosphere of a given school. While hard to provide a concise description of a school environment, most researchers say it is a multidimensional construct that includes academic, social and physical dimensions.

In contrast with the past, public schools are more compelled to produce quality results of students' achievement, and with the state standardized tests, it becomes the school's central focus to survive the present age of accountability. School leaders are considering current researches to arrive at sound decisions and maximize their effort and time to ensure increased students' outcomes (Ravitch, 2010).

Manning (2007) as cited by Estanda (2012) expressed that a person, either a leader or a follower, will be most happy and productive in a situation that allows the expression of his social motives. A person needs someone who will provide a spark for action, which someone will most provide energy and purpose for leadership to occur. Conflict management is the method of dealing with conflicts and how these depend on different personality factors. Instead of avoiding conflicts, managers are recognizing, acknowledging and managing them in a proper manner; they use conflict situations as opportunities for individual and organizational development. Conflicts facilitate organizations to change, survive, and improve.

For an organization or group to exist, survive and function, ethical leadership, plays a crucial role. It means, therefore, that in any educational institution the importance of school administrators to run its business toward the desired goal is highly essential. As a leader, he/she should perform his/her administrative and supervisory function at the highest possible level to produce effective schools.

In DepEd Region XII, most of the cases reported to the DepEd Officials are the conflicts arising between the teachers and their superiors. Due to the demand on the quality of instruction that the teachers should render to their students, more often than not, the school principal, department heads, and administrative staff tend to have a misunderstanding with the teachers. In various Districts in DepEd GenSan, the majority of the clamor of the district heads is the school climate in a specific school which it often causes misunderstanding among teachers. It somehow hampers the harmonious environment that is required to produce a conducive learning environment for the students.

Since conflict is seemingly unavoidable, particularly in a scholarly setting, it is essential for administrators to recognize its constructive and destructive effects, to learn how to manage it, and to practically apply management strategies to address it.

This study endeavored to find out the common management styles and dominant school climate of Public Elementary Schools in General Santos City.

The study determined the prevalent conflict management style and the dominant school climate of the public elementary schools in the Division of General Santos City during the academic year 2014-2015.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the common conflict management style when analyzed according to:
 - 1.1 educational background;
 - 1.2 number of years in service; and
 - 1.3 district?
2. What is the dominant school climate when examined according to:
 - 2.1 educational background;
 - 2.2 number of years in service; and
 - 2.3 district?
3. What is the dominant school climate when analyzed according to the common conflict management styles?

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This study is anchored on Morton Deutsch cooperative model. One of the first to develop insight into the beneficial consequences of cooperation as an academic inquiry. In his view, a variety of factors are important in deciding the form of orientation a party will bring to the negotiation table in its effort to settle the conflict, such as the essence of the dispute and the objectives each party aims at. In addition, Deutsch forecasts the form of interactions that will take place between negotiating parties as a result of their style of conflict. The party's cooperative nature would invoke an environment of confidence and potentially lead to mutually beneficial settlement options. Competitive strategy, on the other hand, results in win-lose results. This strategy appears to exacerbate party hostility and distrust and is usually considered destructive.

Two philosophers who promoted cooperative behavior are Roger Fisher and William Ury. They advocated four principles for successful negotiation which are to separate people from the issue; what Fisher and Ury argue is that it lets parties get a clearer view of the fundamental issue; focus on interest, not position; and build a variety of options before contracting.

In relation to the theory on cooperation, conflict transformation theorists, Bush, Folger and Lederach argue that these models could achieve a solution that satisfies the interests and needs of each country. However if negative attitudes formed in each country during the conflict are not addressed, they may help to generate more conflict a while later. Whereas conflict transformation aims at a fundamental shift in individual attitude and/or actions and/or relationship between two or more disputing parties.

Rahim (2003) states that there is a consensus among management scholars that there is no better approach to addressing, controlling or conflict resolution. In the same way, instead of creating a specific conflict management model, he developed a meta-model for conflict types based on two dimensions, concern for oneself, and concern for others, in the same way that a meta-taxonomy was created by DeChurch and Marks (2001).

Managers need a dual perspective marked by considerations for both tasks and individuals, asserting that in most cases, leaders who show the greatest degree of interest for both dimensions will consistently succeed. The conflict-management research was expanded by Kilmann and Thomas (2010) while emphasizing that one of five different management behaviors may be acceptable depending on the situation.

According to Kilmann and Thomas (2010), by occupying an uncooperative-cooperative spectrum, individuals within the company often aim to meet the needs of others. He/she must personally analyze conditions as they occur in the case of a principal and discern where to occupy this spectrum. Too much cooperation can lead to a lack of organizational emphasis on significant objectives, whereas interpersonal relationships can be impaired by a high degree of uncooperative behavior.

Contemporaries of the school environment describe the school climate as the "ethos or spirit" of an institution. Cohen et. al., (2009) further theorize that the school environment relates to the meaning and disposition of school life as embodied in the form of individuals who reflect their norms, ambitions, values, interpersonal relationships, teaching and learning methods, and organizational structures. Cohen emphasizes the work of Freiberg (1999) as he attempts to describe the school atmosphere as much as we have never noticed the air we inhale before air pollution sickens us.

As Jankens (2011) quoted in his report, "An Examination of the Relationship between School Climate and Student Growth in Selected Michigan Charter Schools" constructed much of the definition and theory of organizational climate of school climate groundwork. His climate-related terms taxonomy offered a detailed specification of the constructs dealing with the entire climate situation.

While the quest for ways of improving schools is not recent, current reform efforts illustrate its significance. Various situations have affected the success of the school, and they have given an insight into new ways of improving schooling. School climate is one of those variables and has been researched for more than four decades, with varying focus, from some perspectives.

The Significance of the Study

School administrators, staff, students, stakeholders, and prospective researchers will benefit from the results of the study. The results of this research will provide the Department of Education with a statistical image of the many forms of conflict management of the General Santos City Public Elementary Administrators and their school environment.

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DEPED Administrators. The findings of this study will help us determine the best-suited styles of conflict management while holding seminar workshops with the implementation of the division's School Administrators/Principals/School heads. The School Administrators. The outcome of the study will help them recognize their personal views about conflict; with greater composure and more optimistic results, they will learn how to overcome conflict. They will also establish the origins of conflict, how to turn emotional conditions into a collaborative atmosphere, and how to negotiate terms that are mutually satisfying. Teachers. The outcome of the study would help them understand the role of the principals of the school when they function in difficult circumstances.

Students. The study's outcome would assist them to achieve a substantive and well-defined school environment that will lead to better acquisition of information. Stakeholders. The result of the study will help them understand how to maintain peace and harmony in the community. Future Researchers. This study will help them open new boundaries about conflict management styles and school climate for other researches to explore. This study was delimited in determining the common conflict management styles and dominant school climate of Public Elementary Schools in General Santos City during the school year 2014-2015. Also, it was delimited in all central or big schools within the District of the Division. The Public Elementary School Teachers served as respondents of the study.

Operational definitions of the terms used in this study are provided for uniformity of understanding: Prevalent Conflict Management Styles. The term refers to the method used to settle a conflict or dispute in a given situation by school administrators, such as collaborating style, competing style, avoiding type, harmonizing style, and compromising style. Avoiding. This refers to the techniques utilized by school administrator that tends to stay away from someone or something that can lead to disarray. Collaborating. This refers to the techniques utilized by school administrator that made someone to work with someone else for a special purpose. Competing. This applies to the school administrator's tactics, which is a "win-lose" strategy. Without requesting support from the group, the administrator acts in an insistent manner to accomplish results, and it may be at the detriment of the other group members. Compromising. This refers to the techniques utilized by school administrator that is a "lose-lose" scenario where neither party really achieves what they want. This requires a moderate level of assertiveness and cooperation Harmonizing. This refers to the techniques utilized by school administrator that blends all aspects of the organization in spite of the differences of its textures. School Climate. It refers to the school's working condition and human relationship working as a group. It also applies to the quality and character of school life. It is founded on designs of school life practices and mirrors customs, aims, standards, social associations, education and leadership methods, and organizational framework, like: autonomous climate (conducive and appealing environment), club climate (enabling environment), controlled climate (projected with stiff implementation of policies and regulations), and closed climate (dominant decision carried by the person-in-charge). Autonomous. This is the kind of school climate that is apparent inside a pre-agreed management system that exhibits freedom of decision-making. Club. This is the type of school environment in which the principal, organization, and other stakeholders exhibit a social spirit. Controlled. This is the type of school environment that shows that all activities are under the principal's central control. For other stakeholders, there are very few ways to take the initiative. Open. This is the type of school environment the principal exhibits as a facilitator, there is a pleasant relationship among teachers, pupils, parents and the community.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following pieces of literature are based on the different researches which are found to have similarity and have bearing on the study about common conflict management styles and dominant school climate of public elementary schools.

Conflict Management in Organization

O'Neill's (2011) research entitled "An Integrative Model of Conflict and Conflict Management in Organizational Work Teams" supports the differentiation and resolution of conflict type variables, conflict management variables, and two emerging conflict interventions involving contextual task conflict. An integrative model, based on a systematic analysis of current empirically constructed and validated science. Although task conflict has either not affected team results or had a deleterious impact, there have been signs that when handled cooperatively and non-competitively, low task conflict levels are advantageous. It is therefore recommended that professionals, coaches, and team leaders develop teams with a low level of team conflict until a more favorable view of task conflict is validated by further study.

As cited by O'Neill (2011), Lunenburg and Ornstein (2008) note that, given the current active emphasis on accountability and student achievement, conditions under which tension is likely to increase for teachers and administrators are increasing. Disputes within a school's skilled workers are likely to arise even in less-demanding circumstances. The potential for disagreement between the organization's interests and those of the individual workers was recognized in their early study of organizations by theorists.

As quoted by Boucher (2013), Schein (2010) notes that conflict is inherent in various organizations, and the role of the leader is its management. The position of conflict and the leader's response to it has also shifted in the evolution of the organization's existence. Conflict is harmful to organizations, as perceived by early organizational theorists. Still, however, it is considered a natural occurrence, a common human condition that is to some degree still present. Moreover, organizational learners see an organization's success as an unresolved conflict rather than a deterrent factor. How conflict is treated has a potential impact and effect on the performance of the organization.

Conflict management, as defined by businessmen, is the application of the ability to sensibly, objectively, and efficiently recognize and resolve or handle conflicts. As wars in business are a natural part of the workplace, there must be people who understand disputes and know how to resolve them. More than ever, this is critical in today's market. Everyone tries his/her best to show the business how valuable he/she is. This leads to friction with other members of the team at times.

Conflict management behaviors are mostly according to a dual concern model or similar to it, according to Desivilya et. Al.,(2005), as cited by Kinnander (2011). Consequently, conflict is induced by several interrelated factors within an organization. Managers should, therefore, consider the root causes of conflict and understand how to diagnose them. Some of the most common causes are contact factors, the history of interactions between the parties, human attributes, cognitive factors and systemic factors (Hitt, 2012).

In addition, Hitt (2012) emphasized that the positive viewpoint recognizes conflict as a normal phase of development that positively affects the organization's culture. For all workers, the grievance method establishes a structured grievance mechanism. Inform the workers at all levels of the company that they have the right to respond to any problems. If treated easily and honestly, it will prevent bad feelings from festering and developing into anger and animosity.

Equal voices make it a reasonable opportunity for all parties involved in a dispute to share their views, regardless of their political power or service duration and role. They may become defensive if dispute participants feel like they are being overlooked or are going through a process leading to a scripted outcome. Although listening to managers rather than frontline workers or loyal employees rather than a new employee is enticing, it is also important to note that even the most trusted associates are not infallible. In meditating on a dispute, one must go beyond it by allowing all the opportunity to talk and present their points with equal weight.

According to Ingram (2009), when drafting dispute resolutions, mediation involvement includes both parties. The theory of Management by Objectives (MBO) notes that workers are usually more committed to goals that they have endorsed and developed. The same applies to dispute resolution. The story always has two sides; there should be an equal opportunity for both sides to be understood, thereby providing a stronger solution to the dispute. Instead of simply delaying its occurrence, they should make decisions that would prevent the disagreement from happening again.

Also, Ingram (2009) emphasized that conflict management applied by managers within a business environment requires problem-solving skills, exceptional negotiation skills, and constructive communication to return the attention to the overall objectives of the organization.

Both sides would be considered by an experienced dispute manager while taking multiple situations into consideration. A skilled conflict manager is subsequently able to select the best way for the correct situation and then use each style in a non-harmful way.

Conflict Management Style

Conflict management applied by managers in a corporate setting requires problem-solving skills, excellent negotiation skills, and constructive communication to return attention to overall organization goals. An experienced conflict manager will consider both parties in different circumstances. Subsequently, an experienced conflict manager can choose the right way for the right condition and then use each style non-harmfully. Collaborative pursuits of all concerns by parties through a solution that satisfies both parties are the result of collaboration between parties to address all underlying concerns and attempts to find alternatives to satisfy all of them (Khanaki, 2010).

To win-win a wholly and mutually satisfactory solution, it works with the other party to understand their concerns and express their concerns in an effort.

Integrating is based on a high degree of self-concern. Participants face problems and miscommunication in the integration model and develop solutions that will satisfy the parties involved. Collaboration characterizes this style. Often the product is a new solution not previously practiced by either party (Boucher, 2013).

Collaboration, which is a problem-solving approach requiring the integration of the concerns of each party, is a reflection of an effort to fully satisfy both parties. To arrive at a practical solution suitable for both parties, the following must be considered; integration involving openness, information exchange, and differences review. It's associated with problem-solving, leading to creative solutions. This style is useful to use different individuals' skills and knowledge to arrive at solutions. It may be appropriate to address strategic issues related to goals, policies, and long-range planning.

Known as assertive and uncooperative, competing style seeks for own concerns by using all appropriate powers to succeed in the position and preserve something that is perceived to be truthful at the expense of others (Khanaki, 2009). Meanwhile, dominating is based on low self-concern and concern for others. This style is also known as competing, usually resulting in a win-win result (Boucher, 2013). The competition reflects a desire to achieve one's ends at another's expense. It's also known as a win-lose orientation (Hughes et al., 2009). According to Kinnander (2011), Desivilya et. al., (2005) state that dominating conflict management patterns has high self-respect and a common concern for others.

As quoted by Healing Hearts (2009), Adkins (2006) states that a competing style of conflict management achieves preferred individual results at the expense of others. Forcing uses other authority or formal authority that one possesses to satisfy his concerns without regard to the party's concern that conflicts can be generated.

A leader stresses his position in a competing style without considering opposing points of view. With minimal cooperativeness, such a method is highly assertive, and the objective is to win. In a situation where non-competitive behavior can be exploited, it is used when a person has to make unpopular decisions, deal with vital issues, take quick action, or need protection (Khanaki, 2009).

He also stressed that unmanaged competitive styles result in lower levels of impact on people, vagueness, dawdling actions, and inoperative participation. Some common ways people show include qualifying actions and threatening resignation to make others agree with their views. While continuously selecting competition has undesirable effects on relationships, industries, and principles, selecting the other party in a competitive style is sometimes the right style. It maximizes reaching one's own goals or solving the problem at the expense of the other party's intentions or feelings.

Avoiding style, also known as unassertive and uncooperative, neglects conflict or rejects conflict. The person believes the battle doesn't bother him or others. One chose to avoid the issue in this mode. Avoiding was based on low self-concern and others. This style features suspension, denial, withdrawal, buck-passing, or otherwise (Boucher, 2013). Desivilya et. al., (2005), as quoted by Kinnander (2011), states that avoiding style has serious self-concern and low self-concern. By contrast, avoidance includes non-responsiveness to both parties' issues. It depicts coldness from any party's interest or inattention (Hughes et. al, 2009).

According to Afzalur et. al., (1992), as cited by Copley (2010), avoiding style is associated with low self and other concerns. Accompanied by withdrawal, both a person's concerns and the other party's concerns are usually not met. It was often found to be used when dealing with perceived tactical or minor issues. It is commonly used when the potential ramifications of confronting the other party outweigh conflict resolution benefits.

The avoiding style occurs when a leader fails to fulfill his or her concerns or those of other individuals. Low willpower and low enforcement characterize this design. It aims to pause—usage when there are problems of low priority, such as reducing pressures or buying time. Avoidance is often important when someone is in a quiet position of authority and has little influence over the situation, when someone has to let others solve the dispute, or when the issue is connected with a much bigger problem. Someone has to focus on the core issue. To build skills in this style, someone must use anticipation to know when to turn away, learn to avoid several questions or sensitive issues by using negotiation, and become skilled in the sense of timing and practice is developed, leaving things unresolved.

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As quoted by Healing Hearts (2009), Adkins (2006) notes that groups cannot fix the problem immediately while avoiding conflict management style. They will suspend or escape the dispute in a reasonable way. Escaping is characterized by actions that may ignore or fail to take part in the war. Although some theories define surviving as an undesirable style that perceives anxieties for both parties' purposes, there are different ways to avoid confrontation.

To please the needs of others, accommodation oversees its own issues. It is a kind of selfless kindness, followed by giving in to the desires of others when one chooses not to do so (Khanaki, 2009). This is when someone collaborates to a high degree, and it may be at his own cost, operating against his or her own interests, goals, and desired results. When the other side is the expert or has a better solution, this strategy is useful. In maintaining future ties with the other side, it can also be helpful (Meier, 2014).

One who teams up well with other colleagues is an approachable boss. It is considered to be the manager's differentiation and acts against their own priorities, goals, and expected results of that manager. If the other individual is the expert or has a better solution, this approach is beneficial.

Accommodation represents a mirror image of competition, giving in entirely to everyone's concerns without making any attempt to achieve one's ends. This is regarded as a tactical appeasement (Hughes et. al., 2009). This helps the other faction to meet its needs while disregarding its own.

The welcoming design fulfills others' worries. Low assertiveness and strong cooperativeness are what it is. Its function is to yield. When anyone needs to demonstrate that it is fair, it is acceptable to use it to develop results, build goodwill, preserve harmony, withdraw, or concentrate on unimportant matters. The ability to give way, the ability to be unselfish, the ability to obey rules, and the ability to adhere to the majority include welcoming skills. It requires giving or smoothing the choppy waves of dispute into the desires of others. For the gain of the other side, it means giving up one's goals. Accommodators also quote phrases such as: "I will agree to any ideas you will present." In times of dispute, the result just does not care. Accommodation may be deemed to be the best choice for that situation. Nonetheless, they are urged to learn more skills if housing is the personal style one exploits.

As quoted by Healing Hearts (2009), Adkins (2006) states that all parties consider what is beneficial to others to preserve harmonized relationships in a harmonizing conflict management style before their own interests. Sharing is a strategy characterizing collaboration amid domination and concession. Together both sides agree; they have something so far. Both sides are moderately yet unconditionally happy (Hughes et. al., 2009).

Obliging is based on less self-attention and more significant consideration for others. This style is called accommodation as well. The faction is interested in fulfilling the other's needs without attending to the interests of his own (Boucher, 2013). As Kinnander (2011) cites, Desivilya et al. (2005) note that conflict management's persuasive trends have serious self-concern and deep concern for others.

As quoted by Copley (2010), Afzalur et. al.,(1992) stress that an obligatory style involves low regard for oneself and deep concern for others. This style relates to the effort to minimize discrepancies and illustrate commonalities to meet the other party's needs. For an individual who feels that he or she might be mistaken and that the problem in question is much more important to the other person concerned, it has been considered useful. When a person is willing to surrender in the hope of having something in return, it can be used as a tactic.

Compromising seeks a mutually acceptable alternative that partly satisfies both sides by taking different issues into account and disregarding others by shifting priorities and finding a middle-ground position (Khanaki, 2010). It is founded on mutual interest for oneself and others. It includes giving and taking relationships between the parties, giving up something to find a mutually agreed solution (Boucher, 2013). As cited by Kinnander (2011), Desivilya et. al.,(2005) show that compromise is of moderate concern to oneself and others.

Compromising is the lose-lose situation where what they want is not accomplished by either person or manager. It needs an appropriate degree of firmness and cooperation. It could be suitable for circumstances where a temporary solution is required by anyone or where both parties have equally important objectives.

As quoted by Healing Hearts (2009), Adkins (2006) describes that in a compromising style of conflict management, each party needs to compromise to achieve a mutually satisfactory result. It is an approach to the middle ground and might not be the best result.

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Afzalur et. al.,(1992) argue as quoted by Copley (2010) that compromise is correlated with an in-between level of consideration for both parties. This style typically involves "give and take," where certain components are willingly given up by both sides to make a mutually reasonable decision. This definition is also used where both parties' interests are mutually exclusive or when an impasse has been reached by both parties, who are equally persuasive, such as a trade union and management. It is used when complex strategic challenges are dealt with.

Compromising abilities include the ability to move and hold the conversation open, the ability to discover an appropriate response for all sides, the ability to give up a portion of what someone needs, and the ability to allocate meaning to all aspects of the issue. Compromise is a resource granted and taken. When bargaining, the final agreement is to break the gap between the two positions. Since the agreement does not have a winner, both sides are unable to meet both goals. Working in a company means workers may be involved in a dispute because there are different personalities and perspectives in life for those working together. Consequently, in the workplace, they do not prevent conflicts.

There are four types of the central conflict in general: interpersonal conflict is the first. A relational form can be taken by this type of dispute. Strange aversions or personality variations may be the foundations of this dispute. Without his interference, the manager usually allows his workers to find a solution to their differences, but often he has to step in.

Second, there is an intra-group disagreement. Within an internal party, team, or department, this is a dispute. This includes more than one individual within a group. Understanding is indispensable in every department of the business. Among other items, it helps to preserve efficiency and the disposal of the company. Whenever group members do not agree with each other, the whole system can be influenced by their problems. It is correlated with racial, religious, or gender bias and different variations in personality. A manager may need outside support to fix the issues, depending on how severe the dispute is. At this point, having a reliable or impartial third party who has know-how in dispute management and settling disputes will be beneficial to a manager.

Thirdly, class disputes. It's a dispute between groups, teams, and agencies. Another cluster will unite against one worker party. Such conflicts can emerge from differing rank and group perspectives. Intergroup conflict typically promotes miscommunication or may lead to no communication at all, upsetting an entity's ability to function. By problem-solving techniques or using an internal conflict-resolution mechanism, the manager can try to resolve the problem. Occasionally, the mediator may help discuss conflict issues and other relevant issues. Such dispute forms must be given a solution immediately or it will ruin the organization as the problem continues. Fighting between different groups or teams can challenge organizations' competitiveness.

Fourth, inter-organizational rivalry. It's a conflict between organizations. Inter-agency conflicts arise in three forms: substantive conflict, emotional conflict, and cultural conflict. The substantive conflict occurs when a fundamental disagreement arises between the two organizations. Cultural tension is rooted in social needs and aspirations. This conflict often causes stereotyping and misunderstanding. Inter-organizational disputes can most often be resolved by mediating and appreciating cultural differences (Violeta, 2012). Hitt (2012) describes three kinds of workplace conflicts: personal, substantive, and procedural conflicts.

Leaders of organizations are responsible for creating a work environment that allows individuals to thrive. They must intervene immediately if wars, disagreements, and differences of opinion escalate into interpersonal conflict. If they value the organization and their positive culture, not speaking, it is not an option. Their mediation ability and intervention are critical in conflict-ridden situations (Heathfield, 2013).

The communication gap that often occurs in the classroom is the most prevalent problem. Teachers don't correctly tell a principal about the needs of students. Although teachers understand what students want from teachers and school, teachers cannot say to a principal and the school committee the students' views because there are a few opportunities for teachers to meet a principal. Although teachers meet and communicate the ideas and needs of learners to the principal, the inputs of teachers are denied as the author Heathfield (2013) added.

It was also stressed clearly by Hitt (2012) that under the centralized structure, these conflicts are caused by a one-way communication flow. A potential solution is here. Initially, both a principal and teachers must build for themselves 'mutual respect' and 'mutual trust'. The two-way communication flow is only possible if it is based on mutual respect and mutual

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trust among school members. They try, of course, to have as many chances to meet and listen to others as possible. At this time, with mutual respect and mutual trust, a principal must meet and listen to others.

Hitt said further that teachers need to try to reduce the generation gap. The reduction of the generation gap in a school can guarantee good communication. To reduce it, they need to determine why older teachers, including principals, are resisting modifications. The more ancient teacher accepted evolution, the decentralized structure, and two-way communication flow. He also added that a principal and older teachers worry about whether their privileges may be threatened by a decentralized structure. Therefore, the younger teachers must strive to respectfully consider the circumstances and opinions of the more former teachers. It is the task of the younger teachers to make a principal and the more former teachers involved in a school and classroom renovation.

The foundation of school and classroom development will be formed by good relations between a principal and teachers through a two-way communication flow. All the views of teachers are regarded with respect in the decision-making process. Many alternatives are taken into account at the level of discussion. Even adequate decision-making by consensus is a time-consuming task at the decision level; there must be negotiation and agreement between professional teachers in an organization to gain efficiency and effectiveness in the decision-making process. The school classroom requires a division of administrative labor.

Also, he stressed that there are five possibilities for resolving disputes. The result must meet the interests, advantages, and needs of all parties: lose-lose, win-lose, lose-win, compromise, and win-win. Lose-Lose, neither party, obtains what is initially expected in this dispute result. Losing-lose outcomes are also seen in cases of violence. The aggressor often fails to achieve an initially desired target, such as a promotion or continued work, and through violent actions, he often fails to get real satisfaction. Often the aggrieved cannot achieve the desired workplace harmony and may endure many adverse effects beyond that. Win-Lose or Lose-Win, one party's concerns are met in any of these subsequent cases, while the interests of the other party are not. For the losing party, this result is not helpful and is also not significantly beneficial for the company. Avoidance is not a solution to these effects, but one side may gain only at the detriment of the other when disputes have "zero-sum" or distributive problems. It can force both sides at all costs to satisfy their concerns.

The win-win scenario happens when both side get what they want. Consider a situation in which an increased salary is negotiated by the corporation, but the administration does not have the funds to increase wages. If the firm wanted to embrace special productivity bonuses, a win-win scenario would occur. Increases in efficiency will be followed by cash incentives, thus raising the wage rate of union workers that they sought in the first place. Management would benefit because it would be able to increase efficiency (therefore profit), which in turn would offset the higher pay (Hitt, 2012).

As quoted by Akinnubi (2012), Ogbonnia (2007) describes an effective leader as an individual with the ability to thrive consistently in a given situation and to meet an organization's expectations. Leaders are recognized for their ability to be empathetic to others and promote clear communication. The way the principal runs the school cannot be determined based on its characteristics, which include age, marital status, teaching experience, academic qualifications, and gender.

As stated by Akinnubi (2012), Ike (2000) agrees that principals with long years of teaching know-how perform better in coordinating non-teaching and teaching personnel in the direction of achieving school priorities and goals. Also, as quoted by Akinnubi (2012), Durosaro (1998) argues that as a front-runner, the school principal must be prepared to integrate roles and staff to achieve the expected goal; the achievement of these goals relies solely on his or her organizational management skills. Within the community, the psychological orientation of leadership influences actions.

Akinnubi (2012) states that in conflict management, the principal's qualification plays an important role. In his analysis entitled "Principal's Characteristics and Conflict Management in Kwara State Secondary Schools, Nigeria," the r outcome indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis with the measured r-value of 0.785, which is higher than the crucial r-value of 0.195, at .05 significance level for 498 degrees of freedom. The study suggests a major association between the qualification of the principal and the style of conflict management.

As cited by Vestal (2011), Berry (1994), and DeTurk (2010), the literature comparing conflict-management discrepancies between seasoned and novice managers is sparse. Only research that was linked to the comprehensive quest for the effects of the principal's years of experience in education and administration were generated because experience and conflict management were examined in work-related contexts, only two of them in school settings. No literature was found that

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focused specifically and explicitly on the subject of conflict-management preferences as applied to the degree of experience of the principal. This topic may also help to start a wider debate on the impact of publicity on desired actions in conflict management. To form a convincing theory, the experience-related strand of literature as a whole proved insufficient.

As quoted by Vestal (2011), DeTurk (2010) explores the dispute resolution styles of a group of superintendents from Nebraska using the Thomas-Kilmann Instrument (2007; 1974). He noticed that the five behaviors of conflict management were used to some degree. Regarding the degree of experience, he noticed that the more novice superintendents were more likely than those who were seasoned to work with a peer. More satisfaction with their dispute resolution behaviors was stated by the more experienced superintendents. When analyzing the effects of age and years of administrative experience, they reported no major differences between the conflict-management styles of male and female elementary principals.

Principals with more experience have teachers who have perceived fewer instances of conflict amongst workers. This finding indicates that the opportunity to encourage teachers to operate under a loosely-coupled system could be best exercised by more experienced principals. The important inference applicable to the current study is that conflict management could be best qualified by more experienced principals as quoted by Vestal (2011) from the work of Meiers (2007).

The issue of school climate has been growing for over 100 years and how it affects student outcomes and the way school leaders can help develop their respective school climate. This topic continues to shed light on the best ways to manage disputes within an organization (Cohen et. al., 2009).

Leadership is the technique of inspiring individuals to strive willingly and vigorously towards achieving group goals. The course is the big increase among the stakeholders of the company in the adoption of meaningful change. This means that an organizational position can encompass various goals but become non-personal, so that a personal touch must be in it to become involved.

Leadership consists of these sections, according to Desamito (2010) the first is to have a vision or mission or goal, the second is to express that goal to other team members and to gain their devotion to that goal. The third is to create a strategy to achieve that goal and execute it. Not everyone is born or taught to be a leader, but individual abilities and attitudes, whether directly or from the side, enable him/her to lead. The consequence of the careful application of these abilities is good leadership.

Fullen (2009) describes that leadership in the delivery of change, development, and success are fundamental and necessary. In all organizations, including schools, society expects more and more. Leadership has been the subject of both extensive, in-depth research and popular writing due to this perceived significance.

As a visionary, organizer, cheerleader, and evaluator, the school principal focuses on its development efforts. The leadership of the principal supports and guarantees the effectiveness of the staff development program to help curve the requisite changes in the instructional program. They are expected to perform duties as principals, such as delivering quality instruction, quality teaching services, supporting the school's vision and mission, supervising school operations, coaching, inducing and mentoring teachers on behalf of the public school, and other teaching-learning activities (Batalla, 2014).

As quoted by Recla (2013), Palconit (2007) notes that the heads of the school are the primary people responsible for the three Ps" in the school (People, Program, and School Plant). The leadership level is one of the most critical variables in distinguishing between a good and a failing school head.

To achieve the desired objectives, educational administrators or school heads must acquire the necessary attributes. As superiors, they must be prepared to give credit to others. Once a superior discriminates against a subordinate, he/she may not be expected to be an active or successful worker. It would also come in the form of a deficiency in the output of the employee (Imperial, 2014).

In education, the school head plays a major role. They perform responsibilities within the school and its environment to coordinate, direct and supervise curriculum programs, classroom instruction, and other related activities necessary for the development of the entire school system and the educational objective's achievement, the center of educational excellence (Angeles, 2010).

Effective leadership is critical to improving the school environment, which is influenced by the principal's actions and behaviors (Rhoden, 2012). As quoted by Recla (2013), Miranda (2010) states that school leaders are engaged in supporting their teachers through mechanisms such as insisting on the assessment of teachers and overseeing professional development. They also challenge teachers to reflect on what they do, encouraging them to take new ways to keep them informed and to protect them from any misconduct.

Using their understanding of the situation and skill sets for their teachers, the principals delegate leadership responsibilities to complete the duties. Until the assignment is completed, the delegation can be collaborative, rotating, or simple, depending on what the principal considers necessary for the current situation (Robinson, 2009).

Three reasons why distributed leadership is so popular are provided by Harris and Spillane (2009). It has normative power, first. As leadership models continue to shift from a principal-centered approach to instructional leadership to a more inclusive model, leaders must delegate leadership and responsibilities in a constructive and purposeful way to continue to sustain a high degree of academic emphasis. Second, there is representational power in distributed leadership. As alternative leadership approaches that involve complex collaborative organizational structures arise, leaders need to distribute leadership that encourages multiple shared interactions and support to compensate for the increasing demands placed on the school or district. Finally, distributed leadership, because it has empirical power, is a popular leadership model.

Findings have, however, shown that dispersed leadership has increased teaching and learning. Likewise, the success of distributed leadership is more aligned with teacher perceptions of the school climate (Robinson, 2009).

New secondary school principals' leadership styles have a strong association with the school climate; new school principals share similar leadership styles, new secondary school principals' different leadership styles contribute to a favorable school atmosphere, and new secondary school principals tend to impact the school climate rather than be affected by it (Stratton, 2010).

Climate at School

The climate of the school is a global concept that refers to the features of the environment of a school that influence the academic and social development of students. This includes the quality of teacher-student and peer relationships, learning expectations and support, the degree of connection, and the physical environment of the school environment (Brand, 2008).

The theoretical foundation of the school climate, as stated by Rhoden (2012), is based on the concept of ecological grounding, which considers students in the context of classrooms, schools, and communities. Four assumptions are made in this theory: (a) each student is an inseparable part of a small social system; (b) disruption is seen as discordance in the system; (c) discordance is seen as a disparity between the abilities of the student and the requirements or expectations of the environment; (d) the objective of any intervention is to make the system work.

Anderson (1982), as quoted by Cohen et. al., (2009), creates much of the basis for the school climate from the notions and philosophies of organizational climate. Although educators have recognized the prominence of the school setting (Perry, 1908), it was Tagiuri (1968) who connected the divide between the corporate world and education by integrating the overall environmental value into a school building. His taxonomy of climate-related terms provided an accurate description of the constructs within a school as an organization dealing with the total environmental quality.

He stressed that while there is no commonly agreed definition of school climate, the importance of school climate reflects the combined and individual experiences within a school, as suggested by numerous researchers and educators. Many scholars initially concentrated on a school's visible characteristics and saw the school environment as tangible property, such as a house or its physical state.

According to Hoy et. al., (1991), as quoted by Pretorius and de Villiers (2009), school climate refers to the founding core of a school, psychological and institutional features that give the character of a school, the enduring quality of the entire school experienced by members, describing their collective insights into routine behavior that generally affects the school climate. Openness in primary behavior is evident from openness and concern for the ideas of teachers; it demonstrates the freedom of teachers to freely investigate and act while constructing the routine aspects of the job.

An engaging environment is represented by the principal's indecisive efforts to enforce and uphold control. The principal is rigid and oppressive (high leadership) and does not respect professional competence or the individual wishes of the faculty (low supportiveness). Also, the principal frequently gives the teacher many assignments. A disengaged climate is very different from the climate involved.

The principal is open-minded and supportive (high support), gives the faculty the opportunity to share their ideas (low direction), and does not assign too many duties that cannot be handled by the teacher (low restrictiveness). Virtually the antithesis of the open environment is the closed climate.

Non-supportive, inflexible, and interfering, the principal is. Assigns to the teacher additional work (high restrictiveness), ineffective, controlled, and rigid (high directiveness). Does not endorse the growth of the faculty or the achievements of students (low supportiveness). Closed climates have principals who as a leader, or as a director of events for the school, are unsuccessful. As a result, no real job satisfaction is experienced by any of the stakeholders, and there is no social association.

In a controlled climate, the principal controls all activities. Other stakeholders have few opportunities to take the initiative. In a paternalistic environment, the principal assumes sole responsibility for developing the school climate and acts as a father. In a club climate, there is a social spirit between the main and other stakeholders to the extent that they are considered one big, happy family. Still, there is not necessarily a question of productive achievement of management goals. According to Halpin (1966), an autonomous climate is a type of environment that portrays an atmosphere where teachers have considerable freedom to act. The leader epitomizes enthusiasm and zeal—no external threats or influences. Teachers are keen to teach, and students are motivated to learn. Managers, teachers, students and parents have close relationships (Rapti, 2010). Autonomy is beneficial in a school system because it leads to stronger results and productive output of each organization member (Alliance for the Study of School Climate, 2014).

The principal acts as a facilitator in an open environment, and there is a social relationship between the principal, educators, students, parents and the community (de Villiers, 2009). The association of teachers is described as professional, friendly, and dedicated to the teaching of students. The principal does not limit or direct the responsibilities of teachers. He is in favor of the personal and professional growth of members of the faculty. Hoy (1998) argues that the open environment reflects on the principal's supportive, welcoming, and positive role in the ideas of teachers and his attachment to and dedication to work.

The leader shows genuine concern over the teachers, according to him. In undertaking tasks, he supports staff members and is given freeway; he is cautious not to allow daily roles to interfere with the responsibilities of teachers; teachers are portrayed as tolerant, helpful and revered in the profession in an open school climate; attentive to the needs of students by working hard for the children to succeed in their pursuits (Rapti, 2010).

Contemporaries describe the school environment as an organization's "ethos or spirit." In particular, the school climate denotes the value and atmosphere of school life based on the experiences of school life of individuals and reflecting customs, goals, ideals, relationships, training and learning practices, and organizational structures (Cohen et. al., 2009).

As quoted by Jankens (2011), Freiberg (1999) continues to describe the school climate as much it seems to go unnoticed before something like the air we breathe, is seriously wrong. In addition, the school atmosphere incorporates many of a school's features and characteristics, including physical and psychological conditions, employee leadership skills, and community relationships. The internal characteristics of the school climate are the distinction between schools and the influence of the behaviors of members and their shared values and interpretations of social activities (Rhoden, 2012).

Five management methods are included in this framework: dominating, obliging, avoiding, incorporating, and compromising. One party goes all out to win its target by using the dominant form, resulting in the other party's clash of viewpoints and objectives. Obliging is related to the effort to minimize diversity and to rely on the similarities to satisfy the other party's interests. Integration, on the other hand includes transparency, knowledge exchange, the quest for solutions, and the analysis of discrepancies to address the issue acceptable to both sides. Finally, compromise requires giving-and-taking, in which both sides give up something to reach a mutually reasonable decision (Rahim, 2002).

Educators play an important role as leaders in schools and classrooms, modeling positive, inclusive, and respectful language and behavior. In order to help achieve a promising school climate, boards and schools should enthusiastically support positive behaviors that reflect the code of conduct, fairness and comprehensive education policy of their board and character improvement initiatives. As part of the school community, they should also invite members of the wider community to become involved in this effort.

School climate is not a stagnant concept, but rather a condition that needs to be monitored and cultivated that constantly changes. As the school leader, the principal monitors the climate and adjusts processes and practices to maintain a healthy and flourishing environment. Principals are motivated to create and maintain favorable school environments because they share the high morale of the school and find interaction with teachers and the community an asset in the development and implementation of teaching (Palestini, 2011).

The principal's leadership activities directly influence the school environment. The capacity of the principal to inspire the staff and to promote the production of quality teaching methods influences the students' progress. Principals are accountable for creating a collegial, collaborative atmosphere that focuses on improving teachers and students during the educational process. Principals foster teacher morale, parent relationships, and professional collegiality by setting the house's mood, which influences the delivery of instruction to students. High teacher morale improves job satisfaction and the sense of solidarity and pride in school (Fultz, 2011).

The School Climate Improvement Protocol is based on a recurring and continuing phase of preparation, evaluation, awareness of the results of evaluation and action planning, implementation of action plans, and re-evaluation, taking into account the continuous cycle of growth efforts. NSCC periodically links with schools to assist them in evaluating and enhancing their learning environments. The refinement of this method is often chosen mainly through the direct reaction of members of the school community who use these guidelines vigorously in their schools. At NSCC, these phases form the basis for the effective and continuous improvement of the entire school (National School Climate Center, 2014).

Among researchers, there is a difference in opinion as to whether the environment is a property of the schools or the subjective interpretation by the school participants. Many researchers conclude that the environment is a property of the school and encountered by parents, teachers, employees, and administrators in their encounters with the school.

The contrasting view holds that the environment within the school is a psychological property of the individual. Based on personal characteristics and expectations, the humidity would be different for each individual in this scenario. Until school climate interventions can be considered, the dispute about whether the school climate is a property of the school, the person within the school, or both, must be resolved. The presumption that the school climate is an individual's psychological property means that the atmosphere will be diverse for any school group partner. The degree to which people agree on climate variables could be calculated and used to determine the climate in schools. The average environment within the school is still significant, and it is possible to combine inter-related agreement ratings to form a climate quality (Scallion, 2010).

Climate was seen mainly as a generic concept to prompt the continuing norm of the framework of the company. B. As quoted by Hoy et. al., (2013), H. Gilmer (1966) defines the organizational environment as distinct characteristics that set the organization apart from others and influence the success of individuals in organizations.

As cited by Hoy et. al., (2013), George Litwin and Robert Stringer (1968) incorporate perception into their description of climate as a set of quantifiable characteristics of the working atmosphere based on the combined insights of people living and working in the environment and shown to affect their behavior." There has been some consensus on the fundamental characteristics of the organ over the past few years. Marshall Poole (1985) encapsulates the deal as follows: (a) regulatory environment is based on large units; it explains properties of the organizations as whole or essential subunits, (b) organizational climate describes a unit of the organization rather than evaluate it or defines sensitive reactions to it, (c) organizational climate rises from habitual organizational habits that are signify.

As cited by Cayubin (2012), Forehand et. al., (1964) show that an organizational environment is a state of an organization viewed by the workers. This is the impression of the work site by the staff and the perspective of the teacher in the teaching-learning environment.

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Efficiency, inspiration, and job satisfaction can be inspired by the environment. This is achieved by creating employee viewpoints on what effects various behavior would have. Employees expect unique incentives, happiness, and dissatisfaction from their knowledge of the environment of the company. A long-term proposal is to have a stable climate. Managers ought to take an environmental asset approach, which means that they are an organizational asset with a long view of the atmosphere. Unwise discipline and pressure among individuals can temporarily increase better efficiency but at the cost of the atmosphere-called asset. An organization like this will inevitably suffer from depleted funds (Valesky, 2011).

Cohen et. al., (2009) describe the school environment as the nature and character of school life based on the commitments of people to school life and mirrors priorities, norms, ethics, relationships, teaching and learning activities, and systems of organization.

Synthesis

Conflict occurs when individuals have different desires, beliefs and opinions and do not see compromise as an opportunity to develop a harmonious relationship with others. Instead of disagreeing, it is often better to change values to find a solution to the problems. Conflicts and discrepancies, if not resolved, only result in more complicated problems.

Conflicts only add to the friction and can complicate the working environment. It leaves a person exhausted and destroys one's credibility. Rather than addressing it, the most realistic thing to do is to postpone conflict. To prevent confrontation, steps must be taken at the right time and in the right circumstances. Leadership happens at various levels and in all areas of society. The overall success of the company or the method is the shared goal that motivates leaders. It becomes apparent after defining leadership as a framework that an awareness of the link between leaders and their constituents is crucial. In addition, the growth and management of effective organizations require leaders to understand the organization's ethos, to respond to the environmental challenges, and to respect the organization's constituents. Hence, leaders must ensure that each member of the organization is part and parcel of the effective structure contributing to fluid movement to ensure the organization's achievement.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study model used by the author was survey research design, particularly a cross-sectional research design. A cross-sectional survey gathers data at one point in time to draw inferences about a population of interest (universe). As snapshots of the populations about which they collect data, cross-sectional surveys have been identified. Cross-sectional surveys can be replicated periodically; however, respondents to the survey at one point in time are not deliberately sampled again in a repeated cross-sectional survey, although a respondent may be randomly selected for a subsequent one for one administration of the survey. In this way, cross-sectional surveys can be compared with panel surveys, for which the individual participants are tracked over time. Generally, panel surveys are carried out to assess changes in the population being examined (Lavrakas, P. J., 2008).

It was a method that suits the research because the researcher's goal was to find out the existing conflict management styles and the dominant school climate of public elementary schools, considering the place where the study was performed among sixteen (16) schools in General Santos City. According to Aggarwal (2008), as cited by Salaria (2012), descriptive research is devoted to collecting data on the prevailing circumstances or situations for description and interpretation. This type of research method is not only amassing and tabulating facts but also includes proper analyses, interpretation, comparisons, identification of trends, and relationships.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in sixteen (16) Districts of Public Central Elementary or Big schools in the Division of General Santos City, Region XII, during the school year 2014-2015. The DepEd Division of General Santos City is divided into districts based on its strategic location.

As of the school year 2014-2015, the respondents were the teachers of Public Elementary Schools in General Santos City with regular permanent status. The 227 respondents were chosen via stratified random sampling process, although the Slovin formula was used among the 904 population to decide how many respondents from the population of these sixteen (16) large schools in the Division of General Santos City of Region XII are to be included in the sample. They were divided into smaller groups or strata based on shared characteristics

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The questionnaire was used by the researcher in gathering the data to determine the common conflict management styles and the dominant school climate in public elementary schools as experienced by the respondents. It consisted of three parts:

Part I dealt with the Profile of School Administrators regarding: educational background, number of years in service, and the district where they belong.

Part II dealt with the Conflict Management Style of School Administrators using a questionnaire adapted from the Conflict Management Styles Survey by Adkins (2010). It consisted of 15 statements in which the respondents answered each statement that provided strategies in dealing with conflict. The respondents rated each statement using a scale of 1 to 4, indicating how likely they used this strategy: 1=Rarely, 2=Sometimes, 3=Often, and 4=Always.

The respondents answered the questions indicating how they behave rather than how they think or should behave. The respondents must be sure to answer the questions indicating how he or she would behave rather than how he or she believes he or she should act. 1=Rarely, 2=Sometimes, 3=Often, and 4=Always.

For identification of the conflict management style of the Public Elementary School Administrators in General Santos City as perceived by the public elementary school teachers, the following was considered as a basis for scoring: the sum of responses on items 1, 5, and 7 refers to collaborating conflict management style. The sum of responses on items 4, 9, and 12 refers to competing, 6, 10, and 15 refers to avoiding, 3, 11 and 14 refers to harmonizing and 2, 8, and 13 for compromising.

Collaborative method, problems would be solved in ways that provide everyone involved with an optimal outcome. Both sides get what they want, and it minimizes terrible feelings. Competing Style, authoritarian approach. Avoiding Style, the non-confrontational approach. Harmonizing Style, giving in to maintain relationships. Compromising Style, the middle-ground approach.

After getting the total scores as identified per conflict management style, the one that receives the highest total score will be the prevalent conflict management style.

Part III dealt with the School Climate Questionnaire adapted from the Alliance for the Study of School Climate (2014). It consisted of 8 subparts: physical appearance, faculty relations, pupils' interactions, leadership/decisions, discipline environment, learning/assessment, and attitude and culture. Each sub-part consisted of five statements wherein; the respondents rated them using the Likert 5-point Scale. After getting the mean of the school climate as a whole, the following was utilized to determine the type of school climate that exists.

Open climate, the principal acts as a facilitator, and there is a cordial relationship between the principal, teachers, learners, and the parent community. In autonomous environment, much freedom of decision-making within a pre-agreed management framework is evident. The members of the governing body, the principal, and the leadership team are, however, actively involved in coordinating the implementation of the management plan to ensure that no one functions outside the management framework. In a "Club" climate, there is a social spirit between the principal and other stakeholders, to the extent that they may be regarded as one big, happy family. Still, there is not necessarily any question of attaining management objectives productively. In controlled climate, all activities are under the central control of the principal. In closed climate, the principal is not as successful as a leader or coordinator of the school's activities. As a result, none of the stakeholders experience any real job satisfaction, and there is no social mingling (de Villiers, 2009).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Prevalent Conflict Management Style of Public Elementary School Administrators when Analyzed According to their Educational Background

It shows the common conflict management styles of public elementary school administrators regarding their educational background. Five (5) or 50 % out of 10 MAEd Full-fledge School Administrators exhibit a harmonizing conflict management style. It implies that the School Administrators try to meet their teachers' expectations, but they might not get what they want. It is a small price to pay for keeping the peace, however. The result conforms to what Khanaki (2010) has stated that an accommodating or harmonizing conflict management style overlooks own concerns to satisfy those concerns of others. It is a form of selfless generosity, followed by yielding to others' wishes when one would prefer not to do. Three (3) or 75% out of 4 school administrators with MAEd units earned exhibit collaborating management style. It means that

the school administrators explore issues with others to find solutions that might meet everyone's needs. As stressed by Hughes et. al., (2009), the collaboration reflects an effort to fully- satisfy both parties. It is a problem-solving approach that requires the integration of each party's concerns. Lastly, school administrators who are full-fledged Ph. D degree holder and with Ph. D units earned both exhibits harmonizing conflict management style.

With this evidence, it can be assumed that the greater an administrator's educational achievement, there is propensity to become a far more flexible leader that can either be a partner or a harmonizer. She/he can blend symphonically and can bring the entire organization into consonance. Hence, it can be concluded that the qualification or educational background affects the administrator's conflict management style. It conforms to what Akinnubi (2012) has posited that the principal's qualification plays a significant role with conflict management style based on the results of his study entitled "Principal's Characteristics and Conflict Management in Kwara State Secondary Schools, Nigeria. It indicates that a significant relationship existed between the principal's qualification and their conflict management style.

Prevalent Conflict Management Style of Public Elementary School Administrators when Analyzed According to Number of Years in Service

It shows the common conflict management styles of public elementary school administrators, when analyzed according to their number of years in service. Two or 50% out of 4 school administrators with 0-5 years range of service and two or 50% out of 4 school administrators with 16-20 years range of service exhibit harmonizing conflict management style. It means that she/he cooperates to a high-degree at her/his own expense that might work against her/his goals and objectives. Adkins (2006), as cited by Kinnander (2011), states that the obliging or harmonizing conflict management pattern notes that there is little consideration for oneself and a vital concern for others in the clear or harmonizing conflict management pattern. The most extended period of tenure among 16 school administrators is within 26-30 years. One or 100% exhibits a harmonizing conflict management style. It implies that the school administrator has a low concern for self and serious concern for others. It conforms with Adkins (2006), as cited by Healing Hearts (2011), which has stated that in an accommodating conflict management style, parties often place the interests of others over and above their interests to maintain a harmonized relationship.

The number of years in service affects how the school administrator spells out his/her conflict management style. The findings support Vestal's (2011) idea that the more inexperienced superintendents collaborated with peers more than those experienced, the more experienced superintendents reported more satisfaction with their conflict resolution behaviors. Principals with more experiences have teachers who perceived fewer instances of staff conflict. This finding suggests that more experienced principals may be better at practicing the skill of enabling teachers to work under a loosely-coupled structure.

Prevalent Conflict Management Style of Public Elementary School Administrators when Analyzed According to District

It shows the common conflict management styles of public elementary school administrators when analyzed according to district. Seven (7) or 43.75 % out of 16 districts exhibits a harmonizing conflict management style. Adkins (2006), as cited by Healing Hearts (2009), explains that in a harmonizing conflict management style, both parties consider what is beneficial to others before their interests to maintain harmonized relationships. Sharing is a method that characterizes cooperation amid dominance and concession. Together, both parties compromise; hitherto, they get something. Both parties are moderately but incompletely satisfied (Hughes et. al., 2009). Seven (7) or 43.75 % out of 16 Districts exhibits collaborating conflict management style. It shows that in these districts, the teachers work with one another to achieve or do something. Boucher (2013) stressed that integrating was based on a high degree of concern for self and others. In this mode, participants confront problems and miscommunication and look for solutions to the problem that will satisfy all parties. This style should be characterized by collaboration. Often the product is a new solution not previously put forth by any of the involved parties. It reveals that school administrators can work jointly with others, especially in an intellectual endeavor. They also show concern for others.

It conforms to what Afzalur et. al., (1992) as cited by Copley (2010), have stated that collaborating should be characterized by both deep concerns for self and others. It involves openness, exchange of information, and examination of differences to reach a solution acceptable to both parties. It can be associated with problem-solving, which may lead to creative

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solutions. This style has been found to be useful in utilizing the skills and information of different individuals to generate solutions and may be appropriate in dealing with strategic issues relating to objectives, policies, and long-range planning. Collaborating managers become partners to achieve their goals in this style. It is how managers break free from the win-lose paradigm and seek a win-win. It can be useful for complex scenarios where managers need to find a novel solution. The data also show further that the common conflict management styles of public elementary school administrators in General Santos City are harmonizing and collaborating conflict management styles.

Dominant School Climate of Public Elementary Schools when Analyzed According to Educational Background of their School Administrators

It shows the dominant school climate of public elementary schools when analyzed according to the educational background of their school administrators. Seven (7) or 70% out of 10 MAEd full-fledged school administrators and 1 out of 1 or 100% school administrator with Ph. D units earned exhibits autonomous school climate. The findings implied that the school administrators have the power and right to govern themselves and the entire school system. They provide freedom to their subordinates in the decision-making that brings about goodness to the whole system. The result conforms to de Villier's (2009) idea that in an autonomous climate, much freedom of decision-making within a pre-agreed management framework is evident. The members of the governing body, the principal, and the leadership team are actively involved in coordinating the implementation of the management plan to ensure that no one functions outside the management framework. Three (3) out of 10 or 75% school administrator with MAEd units earned and 1 out of 1 or 100% school administrator with a full-fledged degree of doctor of philosophy exhibit an open school climate.

It is noted by the researcher that her/his leadership is systematic and well-coordinated. Things work and get fixed immediately. As stressed by de Villiers (2009), in an autonomous climate, the principal acts as a facilitator, and there is a good relationship between the principal, teachers, learners, the parent, and the community.

Dominant School Climate of Public Elementary Schools when Analyzed According to Number of Years in Service of their School Administrators

It shows the dominant school climate of public elementary schools when analyzed according to the length of service of their school administrators. Three (3) out of 4 or 75% of school administrator with 0-5 years range of service and 4 out of 7 or 57.14% of school administrator with 6-10 years range of service exhibit an open school climate. Four (4) out of 4 or 100% of school administrator with 16-20 years of service and 1 out of 1 or 100% school administrator with 26-30 years range of service exhibit an autonomous school climate.

The data revealed that the public elementary school administrators' number of years in service is distinct from each other and their respective school climate. New school principals/administrators can exhibit a desirable school climate just as the seasoned one did. With this phenomenon, it can be concluded that the number of years in service of school administrators does not affect the school climate. It conforms with Stratton (2010), who stipulated in his study "The Impact of New Secondary School Principals on School Climate," that leadership styles of new secondary school principals have a positive correlation with school climate. New school principals share common leadership styles. Various leadership styles of new secondary principals contribute to a favorable school climate, and new secondary school principals tend to influence school climate rather than be affected by it.

Dominant School Climate of Public Elementary Schools when Analyzed According to District

It shows the dominant school climate of public elementary Schools in General Santos City Division when analyzed according to District. Nine (9) out of 16 or 56.25% of public elementary school districts exhibit an autonomous school climate. The data elucidate that most public elementary schools in General Santos City show independence and can govern themselves, which leads to a more desirable outcome. The result conforms to what the Alliance for the Study of School Climate (2014) highlighted that autonomy is beneficial in a school system because it leads to more robust results and productive outputs of every organization member. Seven (7) out of 16 or 43.75 public elementary school districts exhibit an open climate.

It shows that the public elementary schools in General Santos City possessed desirable working condition which promotes cooperation, leads to qualitative delivery of knowledge and helps the progress of quality education. The results conform to

Hoy's (2011) idea. He emphasized that an open climate be characterized by teachers' relations that are professional, collegial, friendly, and committed to the education of students. The principal is supportive and professional and does not restrict nor direct teachers with orders.

Dominant School Climate of Public Elementary School when Analyzed According to Prevalent Conflict Management Style

It shows the dominant school climate of public elementary schools in General Santos City Division when analyzed according to the prevalent conflict management style. Seven (7) out of 16 or 43.75% of public elementary school administrators exhibit a collaborating conflict management style. . The result shows that the administrators of public elementary schools in General Santos City model cooperation and willingness to assist their subordinates instrumentally. They can work with another person or group to achieve or do something. The result conforms to the idea of Adkins (2006) as cited by Healing Hearts (2009) that in collaborating conflict management style, both parties get what they want, and negative feelings are minimized by both parties. Problems are solved to achieve an optimal and win-win outcome.

In collaborating, teamwork and cooperation help everyone achieve his or her goals while also maintaining relationships. It also complies with Culbertson (2014), as he argued that collaborating in working through disagreements would lead to innovative solutions. to satisfy both parties' concerns. Nine (9) out of 16 or 56.25% of public elementary school administrator exhibit an autonomous school climate. The administrators of public elementary schools in General Santos City provide independence to every school system member. They are sympathetic and exemplify fervor. It conforms to Halpin (1966) as cited by Rapti (2010) has declared that an independent school climate is a type of climate that portrays an atmosphere where teachers have, at their disposal considerable degree of freedom to act in school. The leader epitomizes the model of enthusiasm and zeal. There are neither external threats nor influence. Teachers have strong desires to teach, and students are motivated to learn. There is a close relationship between managers, teachers, students, and parents. With this phenomenon, it was observed by the researcher that the public elementary schools in General Santos City are collaborators and shows autonomy in their respective management duty.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following are recommended. General Santos City Division Officials may continue providing professional development among public elementary school administrators in General Santos City. Public Elementary School Administrators in General Santos City may continually seek a mutually-acceptable solution that resolves the conflict. The teachers may make use of the findings of this study to better understand the different climate of an organization and conflict resolution.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn: The typical conflict management style of public elementary school when analyzed according to educational background, the number of years, and the district were collaborating. The dominant school climate when analyzed according to educational background, the number of years and the district was autonomous. The dominant school climate, when analyzed according to prevalent conflict management style, was autonomous.

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